

Syntheses and characterization of citronelloxy dichloro phosphine derivatives of dialkyl ammonium dithiophosphates and dialkyl phosphonates

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Abstract : Dialkyl ammonium dithiophosphates and sodiodialkylphosphite derivatives of citronellol (2-methyl-5-prop-1-en-2-yl)cyclohex-2-enone have been synthesized by treating a benzene solution of phosphorus trichloride with sodium salt of citronellol and then with corresponding dithiophosphate and phosphonate ligand in 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar ratios. The complexes isolated are light yellow coloured viscous liquids soluble in common organic solvents and are characterized by elemental analysis and spectroscopic (IR, PMR and ^{31}P NMR) measurements.

Keywords : Citronellol, dialkyl ammonium dithiophosphate, dialkyl phosphonate.

Introduction

A lot of work had been reported on organic, metal and organometallic derivatives of *O,O'*-dialkyl/alkylene dithiophosphates and dialkyl phosphonates¹⁻¹⁰ from our laboratories during the last decade. In continuation of our earlier investigation into the synthesis and properties of phenyl acetyl, *p*-methyl benzoyl¹¹, 2-alkylene dialkyl dithiophosphato-2-oxo-1,3,2-dioxaphosphorane¹² and phosphorus trichloride¹³, *N*-Bromosuccinimide¹⁴ derivatives of alkyl dithiophosphates, we are interested in extending the investigation on the citronelloxy dichlorophosphine derivatives of dialkyl dithiophosphates and dialkylphosphonates. A lot of work has been carried out on the organic¹⁵, organometal¹⁶ and transition metal derivatives of ligands such as dialkyl phosphonates, dithiophosphates (dialkyl, alkylene). Mainly vanadium complexes¹⁷ of the dithiophosphates, triorganogermanium, alkyne phosphonates, Co^{II} organophosphates materials¹⁸, aluminium methyl phosphonates¹⁹, metal dithiophosphates $\text{M}(\text{DTP})^{20}$ [$\text{M} = \text{Fe}, \text{Cu}, \text{Zn}, \text{Hg}, \text{Sn}$], gallium diphosphates, Pt^{II} complexes containing ferrocene²¹, derived phosphonate ligands showing anticancer activity but no work was done on phosphorus, phosphonate and phosphate esters derivative of eugenol, carvone, citronellol and their metal complexes are virtually unknown in the world of chemistry. The basic ligand citronellol is well known component of rose oil and the chemistry of this

component is very vast as the compound is used as anti-bacterial agent as a component of odomas (mosquito repellent), anticonvulsant, antifungal and anticancerous agent, so compound prepared by the authors will show pesticidal activity for agricultural and medicinal chemistry. The flavouring component citronellol as well as other terpenoids which are natural products, already have insecticidal/pesticidal^{22,23} activity. Introducing phosphorus ligands on one hand and variety of metal on other hands will definitely enhance the toxicity/pesticidal activity of the resulting complexes.

Results and discussion

The reaction of citronellol had been carried out with sodium metal using anhydrous benzene as solvent. After 5-6 h reflux, sodium salt of citronellol was prepared. To it a benzene solution of phosphorus trichloride was slowly added at room temperature with stirring and after complete addition and refluxing the ammonium salt of dialkyl dithiophosphates was added in different molar ratio (1 : 1, 1 : 2) and then contents were refluxed for 10-12 h to ensure completion of the reaction. The reaction seems to be slow and sluggish. A yellow coloured viscous liquid was obtained after removing $\text{NaCl}/\text{NH}_4\text{Cl}$ and solvent under reduced pressure. The reaction have been carried out as follows :

Scheme 1

The above reaction have been carried out under the following steps :

C₁₀H₁₉OPCl₂, similar to the above has been allow to react with sodium salt of dialkyl phosphonates (prepared *in situ*) in different molar ratio and then contents have been refluxed for 10–12 h. The product isolated was a light yellow coloured viscous liquids after removing NaCl/NH₄Cl and solvent under reduced pressure.

The above reactions have been carried out under the following steps :

The above complexes are soluble in common organic solvent. It has been observed that the 1 : 2 derivatives are more stable in nature in comparison to 1 : 1 derivatives.

All the complexes have been characterized by elemental analysis and spectroscopic analysis (IR, PMR, ³¹P NMR) which are discussed below :

Note

Scheme 2

IR spectra :

The IR spectra of the above derivatives show the disappearance of a $\nu(O-H)$ absorption band present at $3400-3300\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in citronellol. The characteristic stretching vibration $\nu(P-O-C)$, $\nu(P=O)$ and $\nu(P-Cl)$ have been appeared at $1040-1150$, $1244-1255$, $500-530\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and absorption band for $\nu(P=S)$ appeared at $800-900$ and $650-670\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and a new absorption band appeared for $\nu(P-P)$ and $\nu(P-S-P)$ at $(340-510, 350-510)$ and $(650-630\text{ cm}^{-1})$ respectively. The $\nu(P=S)$ absorption band appeared in the region $(770-820\text{ cm}^{-1})$. On the basis of above observation it appears that there may be formation of $O=P-P=O$, $P-S-P=S$ and $O=P-P=O$ chemical linkage. Other relevant IR absorption frequencies are listed in Table 2.

PMR spectra :

The PMR spectra of the newly synthesized deriva-

tives contain all the relevant PMR signals of citronellol, dialkyl phosphonates and dialkyl dithiophosphates, except the $-OH$, $P-H$ and NH_4^+ proton signals. The details are listed in the Table 3.

^{31}P NMR spectra :

It is to mention that in dithiophosphate derivatives the ^{31}P signals are present in the region of $\delta 87.66-96.41$ ppm which is due to $(P=S)$ phosphorus atom. There is no ^{31}P signal appeared in region of trivalent phosphorus atom, except in complex number (6) at 92.21 ppm. A ^{31}P signal appears in the region $(8.25-23.9\text{ ppm})$ which seems to be due to oxidation of P^{III} to P^V by consuming atmospheric oxygen ($P^{III} \xrightarrow{1/2O_2} \gg P^V=O$) which is in the region of pentavalent phosphorus atom. phosphonate esters. Whereas in dialkyl phosphonate de-

Table 1. Reactions of citronellol with dialkyl ammonium dithiophosphate and dialkyl phosphonate

I. Analytical data of product

Sl. no.	Reactants (g)				Product Found (Calcd.)	Yield (%)	Found (Calcd.) (%)		
	Citronellol	Na	PCl_3	dtp/ phosphonate			C	H	S
1.	1.56	0.23	1.37	3.50	$C_{10}H_{19}OP-[S_2P(OCH_3)_2]_2$ 4.21 (5.01)	84.03	33.40 (33.60)	5.91 (6.20)	51.10 (51.20)
2.	1.56	0.23	1.37	2.20	$C_{10}H_{19}OP-[P(O)(OCH_3)_2]_2$ 3.43 (4.03)	85.11	40.92 (41.58)	7.10 (7.67)	-
3.	1.56	0.23	1.37	2.03	$C_{10}H_{19}OP(Cl)SP(S)(OC_2H_5)_2$ 3.36 (4.06)	82.75	41.09 (41.32)	7.01 (7.13)	15.34 (15.74)
4.	1.56	0.23	1.37	2.76	$C_{10}H_{19}OP-[P(O)(OC_2H_5)_2]_2$ 3.92 (4.59)	85.40	35.80 (36.52)	7.98 (8.47)	-
5.	1.56	0.23	1.37	3.32	$C_{10}H_{19}OP-[P(O)(O-{}^n C_3H_7)_2]_2$ 4.12 (5.15)	82.00	51.02 (51.16)	8.91 (9.10)	-
6.	1.56	0.23	1.37	2.30	$C_{10}H_{19}OP(Cl)SP(S)(O-{}^i C_3H_7)_2$ 3.50 (4.17)	83.93	44.90 (45.87)	7.70 (7.88)	12.92 (13.37)

Table 2. The assignment of the main characteristic IR absorption bands (cm^{-1}) of citronellol derivatives of dithiophosphates and phosphonate esters

Sl. no.	Compds.	$\nu(\text{P}=\text{S})$	$\nu(\text{P}-\text{Cl})$	$\nu(\text{P}=\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{P}-\text{O}-\text{C})$	$\nu(\text{P}-\text{S}-\text{P})$	$\nu(\text{P}-\text{P})$
1.	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{19}\text{OP}-[\text{S}_2\text{P}(\text{OCH}_3)_2]_2$	820	-	1255	1040 (I) 970 (II)	650	-
2.	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{19}\text{OP}-[\text{P}(\text{O})(\text{OCH}_3)_2]_2$	-	-	1260	1060 (I) 980 (II)	-	440
3.	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{19}\text{OP}(\text{Cl})\text{SP}(\text{S})(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)_2$	770 (I) 800 (II)	660	1260	1040 (I) 960 (II)	650	-
4.	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{19}\text{OP}-[\text{P}(\text{O})(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)_2]_2$	-	-	1260	970 (I) 1040 (II)	-	430
5.	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{19}\text{OP}-[\text{P}(\text{O})(\text{O}-^n\text{C}_3\text{H}_7)_2]_2$	-	-	1260	960 (I) 1050 (I)	-	440
6.	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{19}\text{OP}(\text{Cl})\text{SP}(\text{S})(\text{O}-^i\text{C}_3\text{H}_7)_2$	780 (I) 810 (II)	650	-	1060 (I) 960 (II)	640	-

Table 3. ^1H NMR and ^{31}P NMR spectral data of citronellol derivatives of dithiophosphate and phosphonate esters

Sl. no.	Compds.	^1H NMR (δ ppm)	^{31}P NMR (CDCl_3) (δ ppm)
1.	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{19}\text{OP}-[\text{S}_2\text{P}(\text{OCH}_3)_2]_2$	δ 2.9 ($\text{CH}_2\text{OP}(\text{S})$); δ 3.4 (CH_2OP); δ 4.0 m ($\text{CH}=\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2$); δ 1.5 (CH_3)	δ 96.4; δ 9.35
2.	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{19}\text{OP}-[\text{P}(\text{O})(\text{OCH}_3)_2]_2$	δ 3.9 ($\text{CH}_2\text{OP}(\text{O})$); δ 3.6 (CH_2OP); δ 4.1 m ($\text{CH}=\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2$); δ 1.4 (CH_3)	δ 8.45; δ 2.19
3.	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{19}\text{OP}(\text{Cl})\text{SP}(\text{S})(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)_2$	δ 4.1 ($\text{CH}_2\text{OP}(\text{S})$); δ 3.0 ($\text{CH}_2\text{OP}(\text{Cl})$); δ 4.4 m ($\text{CH}=\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2$); δ 1.0 t (CH_3)	δ 91.4; δ 8.25
4.	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{19}\text{OP}-[\text{P}(\text{O})(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)_2]_2$	δ 4.0 (CH_2OP); δ 3.6 ($\text{CH}_2\text{OP}(\text{P})$); δ 4.2 m ($\text{CH}=\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2$); δ 0.9 (CH_3)	δ 30.9; δ 23.76
5.	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{19}\text{OP}-[\text{P}(\text{O})(\text{O}-^n\text{C}_3\text{H}_7)_2]_2$	δ 3.9 t ($\text{CH}_2\text{P}(\text{O})$); δ 3.9 t (CH_2OP); δ 4.5 m ($\text{CH}=\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2$); δ 1.0 t (CH_3)	δ 30.06; δ 23.9
6.	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{19}\text{OP}(\text{Cl})\text{SP}(\text{S})(\text{O}-^i\text{C}_3\text{H}_7)_2$	δ 4.4 m ($\text{CH}_2\text{OP}(\text{Cl})$); δ 3.5 t ($\text{CHOP}(\text{S})$); δ 4.1 m ($\text{CH}=\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2$); δ 0.4 d (CH_3)	δ 87.6; δ 92.21

derivatives ^{31}P signals observed in the region δ 2.19–23.9 ppm which is indicative of the presence of phosphoryl ($\text{P}=\text{O}$) group in the corresponding products. Only one ^{31}P NMR signal have been observed in phosphonate derivatives in the range of pentavalent phosphorus atom (0–10 ppm) which is only possible due to oxidation of P^{III} to $\text{P}^{\text{V}}=\text{O}$.

In comparison to dialkyl phosphonate ^{31}P (0–10 ppm), the ^{31}P signal has been strongly deshielded and thus appeared in the higher ppm range which is due to formation of complex on one hand on the other hand due to chemical bonding of phosphorus with citronellol. The details are listed in the Table 3.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Solvents

were dried by standard methods whereas dialkyl/diphenyl phosphonate were prepared by the methods reported in the literature²⁴. Sulfur was estimated gravimetrically as barium sulphate²⁵.

The IR spectra were recorded on a FTIR 8400S Shimadzu Japan spectrophotometer in the range 4000–225 cm^{-1} employing KBr pellets and the ^1H NMR and ^{31}P NMR spectra were recorded on Jeol 300 MHz FT NMR system in CDCl_3 solvent. Elemental analysis were performed on a Perkin-Elmer CHN/O analyzer at the CDRI, Lucknow. Analytical results are summarized in Table 1.

Preparation of dithiophosphate derivatives $[(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{19}\text{O})\text{P}\{\text{SP}(\text{S})(\text{OR})_2\}_2]$:

The citronellol (1.56 g/10 mmol) and sodium (0.23 g/10 mmol) were allowed to react in anhydrous benzene

and after complete dissolution of sodium, a benzene solution of phosphorus trichloride (1.37 g/10 mmol) was added to it. To ensure completion of reaction, the contents have been refluxed for one hour. After that ammonium dimethyl dithiophosphate (3.4939 g) was added to it, and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 10–12 h. NaCl and NH₄Cl both (2.2016) were precipitated and filtered off under anhydrous condition. Solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the light yellow coloured viscous liquid (4.2 g, 84%) was isolated.

Preparation of dialkyl phosphonate derivatives

$[(C_{10}H_{19}O)P\{P(O)(OR)_2\}_2]$:

The citronellol (1.56 g/10 mmol) and sodium (0.23 g/10 mmol) were allowed to react in anhydrous benzene and after complete dissolution of sodium, a benzene solution of phosphorus trichloride (1.37 g/10 mmol) was added to it. To ensure completion of reaction, the contents were refluxed for one hour. After that sodium salt of dimethyl phosphonates (2.20 g) was added to it, and the reaction mixture was again refluxed for 10–12 h. NaCl (1.5021 g) precipitated and filtered off under anhydrous condition. Solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the light yellow coloured viscous liquid (3.4 g, 85%) was isolated.

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